

The Impact Of Work Stress, Financial Compensation and Non-Financial Compensation on Employee Employment at A Construction Company In Pekanbaru

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ABSTRACT

This research was done at the Construction Company in Pekanbaru. The aim of this study is to find out the impact of work stress, financial compensation and non-financial compensation on employee job satisfaction at the Construction Company in Pekanbaru. The sample in this study is an employee of the Construction Company in Pekanbaru of 35 people using saturated sampling or census techniques. To analyze the data in this study use quantitative descriptive techniques using double linear regression. Research findings show that work stress, financial compensation and non-financial compensation have a partial impact on employee job satisfaction. At the same time or simultaneously, work stress, financial compensation and non-financial compensation have a significant impact on employee employment satisfaction at the New Construction Company with known F counts of $(35,566) \geq F_{table} (2,91)$ with a significant $0,000 \leq 0,05$, and a determination coefficient (R Square) value of 0,775 equals 77,5% which means that the work stress variables, economic compensation, and nonfinancy compensation affect employee job satisfaction of 77,5%.

INTRODUCTION

According to Robbins, increasing employee job satisfaction in a company can be achieved by several factors that influence employee job satisfaction, namely work motivation, leadership, work stress, career development, work performance, workload, rewards, employee relations, work facilities.

Job satisfaction is basically something that is individual. The level of satisfaction of each individual varies according to the system of values that apply to him. Gases equipment (gas tubes, trolley, regulators, storage tanks, etc), Central gas system (medical gas installation, outlets, flowmeters, etc.), Hydrant, Electrical, Electronics (CCTV, nurse call, MATV, PABX, sound system etc.), Mechanical, Hospital equipment, Procurement of goods K3 (health and safety at work), Medical gases and specialty gases, (O2, C2H2 HP, Argon HP dan UHP, CO2 HP dan UHP, He HP dan UHP, N2 HP dan UHP, O2 HP DAN UHP, etc).

Table 1. Data Turnover of Employees of Construction Companies in Pekanbaru

Years	Num. Of Employees	Num. Of Employpess Entered	Num. Of Employees Left	%
2017	45	4	7	15,5%
2018	42	7	9	21,4%
2019	40	6	8	20%
2020	38	7	10	26,3%

Source :

From the table above it can be proven that the company has an indication of a decrease in the number of employees in each year. According to the results of an interview with one of the employees can be explained intesistas employee exit occurred by several factors, that is, the presence of employee dissatisfaction resulting in turn over each year. The highest turnover was in 2020 of 10 employees with a 26.3% percentage, so we can conclude that the employee satisfaction rate of the Construction Company in Pekanbaru is still low.

According to Mangkunegara, the causes of work stress include overweight workloads, urgent working hours, poor quality of work surveillance, unhealthy working climate, inadequate authority related to responsibilities, work conflicts, differences in values between employees and leaders who are frustrated at work. Based on the results of pre-enquiries that have been carried out with the dissemination of questionnaires to employees of Construction Company in Pekanbaru can be seen that the overall work stress of employees is quite high. This indicates that there is a workload given that feels unfair to employees and also the time given to complete the work must be completed as soon as possible. It leads to employees having to work outside of office hours, and there are even some employees who are carrying home work, which has an impact on their shortage of rest hours.

In addition to the burden of work and time in the completion of the work that is not fair to repay the services given to employees is also unfair this causes a lack of satisfaction in the work and can be indicated also causes work stress. In addition, the occurrence of conflict between employees and leaders as well as the poor physical conditions of the working environment will also result in the emergence of a sense of stress in work. Financial compensation is the most considered compensation by an employee when choosing a job. If the financial compensation of wages, bonuses, and benefits received is not in line with expectations, it will cause employee dissatisfaction.

The results of the interviews show that financial compensation is less applied to the company. This affects employee satisfaction, because companies that provide insufficient compensation are difficult to realize employee job satisfaction. As for the salary given to the employees of the Construction Company in Pekanbaru, calculated for one month using the standardization of the Minimum Wage of the District (UMK) in 2022 which is 3.049.675,79

Table 2. Salary of Construction Company Employees in Pekanbaru

No	Position	Length of Service	Num. Of Employees	Salary (Rp)
1	Directur	5 tahun	1 orang	13.000.000
2	Accounting	2-7 tahun	5 orang	4.000.000
3	Production	1-5 tahun	15 orang	3.300.000
4	Project	1-5 tahun	10 orang	3.150.000
5	Marketing	1-4 tahun	4 orang	3.300.000

Non-financial compensation is any form of reward given by a company in the form of non-money earned by a person from the job itself, or from the psychological, and or physical environment in which the person works. From the survey results can be seen that the company does not provide non-financial compensation to employees which causes employees difficulty in work such as lack of transportation provided, no mess of housing for employees. Therefore, many employees feel dissatisfied with the facilities provided by the company.

The need fulfillment theory states that job satisfaction is measured by the appreciation received by employees or the level of needs satisfied. Officers will be satisfied if they get what they need. There is a positive direct relationship between job satisfaction and actual satisfaction of expected needs. Equity theory, this theory states that people will feel satisfied as long as they feel there is equity, the sense of equity and inequity gained by comparing themselves to others in class, middle office, or elsewhere.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Job Satisfaction

According to Robbins in Wibowo (2016:501) satisfaction is a general attitude towards a person's work, which shows the difference between the amount of reward the employee receives and the amount they believe they should receive. According to Robbins and Judg in Indrasari (2017:39) job satisfaction is defined as a positive feeling about a person's work that is the result of an evaluation of its characteristics. That job satisfaction can be explained by the need fulfilment theory, the equity theorie, the discrepancy theories, the

motivation theory of two factors, and the social reference group theory. The five kinds of theory can be explained as follows:

1. The need fulfillment theory states that job satisfaction is measured by the appreciation received by an employee or the level of satisfied needs. Officers will be satisfied if they get what they need. There is a positive direct relationship between job satisfaction and actual satisfaction of expected needs.
2. The principle of equity theory is that people will feel satisfied as long as they feel that there is equity, equity and inequity gained by comparing themselves to other people in class, middle office, or elsewhere.
3. The discrepancy theory states that to measure a person's job satisfaction, the impulse is to calculate the difference between what is expected of a job and what is perceived. The employee's attitude to his job depends on the perceived inconsistencies.

According to the theory, there are two factors that measure employee satisfaction and dissatisfaction, namely: 1. The maintenance factor or dissatisfice factors are the maintenance factors related to human rights that want to gain satisfaction, including salary, quality of supervision, organizational policy, the quality of interpersonal relationships between colleagues, with superiors and subordinates, job security, status, and working conditions. 2. The motivator or satisfaction factors are related to the psychological needs of employees.

B. Factors Affecting Job Satisfaction

1. Mentally Challenging Work The mentally challenging work factor in employee satisfaction describes that the employee prefers a job that gives him the opportunity to use all his abilities in completing a given job freely.
2. Equitable Rewards Officers want organizational policies in the payment system and promotional opportunities that are fair and in line with expectations. Job satisfaction will be created if wages are paid fairly, in accordance with the scope of the work, the ability of the staff, and the standards in force.
3. Supportive Working Conditions Officers will always pay attention to the working environment to obtain comfort. Officials do not like if the work facilities are unpleasant and dangerous to their safety. Officer wants the work environment atmosphere close to the atmosphere while at home.
4. Supportive Colleagues Officers work not just for money or physical reward. For most employees working is basically to meet the needs of social interaction. Having positive colleague support will provide employee work satisfaction. Leadership behaviour also affects employee satisfaction of work.

C. Work Stress Understanding

According to Mangkunegara (2010:157) Working stress is the feeling of stress experienced by employees in the face of work. This work stress appears from symptoms among other things emotional instability, feeling restless, like to be alone, difficulty sleeping, excessive smoking, can not relax, anxiety, tension, nervousness, increased virgin pressure and experiencing digestive disorders.

According to Rohman (2017:180) Stress is an emotional stress situation experienced by a person who is facing enormous demands, obstacles, and the presence of very important opportunities that can affect one's emotions, thoughts, and physical condition (Djamil, 2023).

D. How to deal with work stress

According to Rohman (2017:187) to deal with stress arising from work can be done with three strategies namely:

1. Minimizing and controlling stress sources In this strategy one must accurately identify the sources of stress causes, make an assessment of the situation, develop alternative actions, take the most appropriate action, take more positive action, use feedback, and so on.
2. This strategy is carried out by controlling the various reactions caused by stress, either physically, emotionally (consciously controlling emotions and getting social support from the skiing environment), or forms of self-defence mechanisms such as crying, telling others, with humor, breaks, and so on.

3. Improving personal endurance The strategy is carried out by self-enforcement, i.e. by better understanding oneself, understanding others, developing personal skills, exercising regularly, being devout, patterns of regular and disciplined work, development of goals and values that are more realistic.

E. Work Stress Indicator

According to Robbins in pane (2020) there are three indicators of work stress, among others:

1. Psychological symptoms, prolonged stress will affect a person's condition b. Behavioral symptom
2. Condition in which an employee will experience unpleasant conditions in doing a job
3. Physiological symptom is a condition where an employer will suffer fatigue as a result of excessive work.

F. Compensation

According to Rivai, dkk (2014:357) Compensation is something that employees receive in exchange for their contributions to the company. Compensation is one of the human resource functions that involves all kinds of individual rewards in exchange for performing organizational duties. Compensation components are the kinds of compensation or rewards, whether monetary or financial or non-financial, received by a person through an employment relationship with an organization or company.

G. Financial Compensation

According to Wibowo in Sahronia (2015) Financial compensation is the most considered compensation by employees in choosing a job. When financial compensation in the form of salary, bonuses, and benefits received turns out not to meet expectations, it will cause employee dissatisfaction. According to Rivai (2014) financial compensation consists of direct and indirect compensation. Financial compensation can be direct compensation given to employees, or indirect, where employees receive compensation in non-monetary forms.

Type of Financial Compensation

1. Wages and salaries Related to the rate of wages per hour (semakin alam jam kerjanya semakin besar bayarannya). Wages are the basis of wages used frequently for production and maintenance workers. Wages generally apply to weekly, monthly, or annual rate payments.
2. Incentives Additional compensation above or beyond the salary or wages provided by an organization or company. Incentive programmes are adjusted by providing additional remuneration based on productivity, sales, profits, or cost reduction efforts.
3. Health and life insurance benefits, agency holidays, retirement programmes, and other benefits related to employment are examples of benefits programmes.

H. Non-Financial Compensation

Non-financial compensation, can be a job (interesting tasks, challenges, responsibilities, recognition and a sense of achievement). kebijakan-kebijakan yang sehat, supervise yang kompeten, kerabat yang menyenangkan, lingkungan kerja yang nyaman, dan lainnya. According to Simamora in Sahronia (2015) non-financial compensation is any form of reward given by a company in the form of non-money earned by a person from the job itself, or from the psychological, and or physical environment in which the person works.

I. Conceptual Framework

Picture 1. Conceptual Framework

Source : Kumpulan Peneitian (2020)

METHODS

A. Population and Sampling Research

The sample in this study is Employees of Construction Companies in Pekanbaru which is as many as 35 people. The sampling technique in this study uses Purposive Sampling.

B. Data collection techniques

Interviews are used as data gathering techniques when researchers want to do preliminary studies to find a problem to be investigated, and also when they want to know things from respondents who are more in-depth and the number of respondents is small.

The likert scale is a scale designed to enable the respondent to answer different levels on each object to be measured. A questionnaire is a data collection technique that is done by giving a set of written questions to respondents to answer

Documentation is a method used to obtain data and information in the form of books, archives, documents, numerical writing and images that are reports and descriptions that can support research.

C. Data Analysis Methods

1) Descriptive Data Analysis

Sugiyono (2016) argues that the method of descriptirf analysis is the statistical method used to analyze data by describing or describing the data collected without intending conclusions that apply to generality and generalization.

2) Quantitative Data Analysis

Sugiyono (2016:8) presented the method of quantitative research understood as a method of research based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research on a particular population or sample, the collection of data using the research instrument of data analysis is quantitatively/statistically, with the aim of testing the hypothesis that has been established. As for the quantitative data obtained from the construction company in Pekanbaru.

D. Data Quality Test

The quality test of the instrument aims to determine the consistency and accuracy of the data collected. How the testing is carried out with the Validity Test and Reliability Test of data obtained through the respondent's questionnaire , A question is said to be reliable if a person's answer to a question is consistent or stable over time.

E. Validity Test

A validity test is used to measure the validity or non-validity of a questionnaire. The validity test can be performed by looking at the correlation between the scores of each item in the questionnaire and the total scores to be measured, i.e. by using the pearson coefficient in SPSS.

F. Rehabilitation Test

The reliability test is used to determine the consistency and reliability of a measuring device, whether the measuring instrument will obtain a consistent measurement if measurements are repeated again. The reliability test in this study uses the Cronbach Alpha technique, and the value can be seen on the processing results using the SPSS program.

G. Classical Assumption Test

To determine whether a regression estimate is free of bias, which results in an invalid regression result and eventually the regression cannot be used as a basis for testing hypotheses and drawing conclusions, the classical assumption is used.

1. Data Normality Test

The normality test is performed to test whether the data examined for the whole indicator and variable is normal.

2. Multicollinearity test

The multicollinearity test is used to test whether in the regression model formed there is a high or perfect correlation between free variables or not.

3. Autocorrelation Test

Autocorrelation is a correlation that occurs between members of a series of observations organized in times series at different times. Autocorrelation aims to test whether in a linear regression there is a correlation between interference errors at the period t if there is an autocorrelation means.

H. Hypothesis Test

1) Partial Test

This test was performed at a significant rate of 5% and the degree of freedom (df) $n-k-1$ compared to t count with the table. If t counts $>$ t tables then H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. This means that the independent variable has a meaningful influence on the dependent variable. On the contrary, when t counts then $<$ t table then H_0 is accepted. And H_a rejected means that the independent has no meaningful influence on the dependent variable.

2) Simultan Test

This test is used to determine the influence of joint free variables on bound variables. Where F counts $>$ F table, then H_0 accepts or jointly the free variable can describe the bound variable simultaneously. On the other hand, when F calculates $>$ F tables, then H_0 accepts, or Jointly free variables can explain the binding variable concurrently.

I. Double Linear Analysis

This research uses quantitative descriptive methods, i.e. the data collected is analyzed by delineating and associating existing theories with existing problems, which will then provide relevant results for further conclusions and suggestions. To determine the magnitude of the influence of a variable, a double linear regression method is used to measure the relationship between a bound variable and two or more free variables.

RESULTS

A. Quality Data Test

Table 3. Validity Test

Variabel	Pernyataan	r hitung	r tabel	Keterangan
Kepuasan Kerja (Y)	Y.1	0,372	0,3	Valid
	Y.2	0,430	0,3	Valid
	Y.3	0,653	0,3	Valid
	Y.4	0,646	0,3	Valid
	Y.5	0,653	0,3	Valid
	Y.6	0,646	0,3	Valid
	Y.7	0,653	0,3	Valid
	Y.8	0,321	0,3	Valid
	Y.9	0,331	0,3	Valid
Stres Kerja (X1)	X1.1	0,420	0,3	Valid
	X1.2	0,558	0,3	Valid
	X1.3	0,516	0,3	Valid
	X1.4	0,478	0,3	Valid
	X1.5	0,535	0,3	Valid
	X1.6	0,420	0,3	Valid
	X1.7	0,543	0,3	Valid
	X1.8	0,441	0,3	Valid
	X1.9	0,543	0,3	Valid
Kompensasi Finansial (X2)	X2.1	0,682	0,3	Valid
	X2.2	0,626	0,3	Valid
	X2.3	0,669	0,3	Valid
	X2.4	0,615	0,3	Valid
	X2.5	0,615	0,3	Valid
	X2.6	0,381	0,3	Valid
	X2.7	0,626	0,3	Valid
	X2.8	0,682	0,3	Valid
	X2.9	0,615	0,3	Valid
Kompensasi Non Finansial (X3)	X3.1	0,682	0,3	Valid
	X3.2	0,392	0,3	Valid
	X3.3	0,682	0,3	Valid
	X3.4	0,392	0,3	Valid
	X3.5	0,682	0,3	Valid
	X3.6	0,682	0,3	Valid
	X3.7	0,392	0,3	Valid
	X3.8	0,453	0,3	Valid
	X3.9	0,362	0,3	Valid

Table 4. Reliability Test

Variabel	Cronbach' Alpha	Nilai	Keterangan
Kepuasan Kerja (Y)	0,660	0,60	Reliabel
Stres Kerja (X1)	0,601	0,60	Reliabel
Kompensasi Finansial (X2)	0,797	0,60	Reliabel
Kompensasi Non Finansial (X3)	0,613	0,60	Reliabel

Cronbach's Alpha value for each variable is greater than 0.60. This indicates that each of these variables is reliable and deserves to be tested on this study.

**Table 5. Reliability Test
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test**

		Unstandardized Residual
N		35
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	1.42050297
	Absolute	.139
Most Extreme Differences	Positive	.139
	Negative	-.107
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.822
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.508

a. Test distribution is Normal.
b. Calculated from data.

Test results with one-sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov test with a significant 0.443 (Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed) greater than 0.005 and can be said that the residual value is normally distributed.

**Table 6. Multicoliniarity Test
Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics		
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF	
(Constant)	1.376	3.345		.411	.684			
1	Stres Kerja (X1)	.318	.119	.336	2.679	.012	.461	2.168
	Kompensasi Finansial (X2)	.239	.070	.352	3.414	.002	.685	1.460
	Kompensasi Non Finansial (X3)	.433	.099	.482	4.362	.000	.595	1.682

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Kerja (Y)

That variance inflation factor (VIF) value ≤ 10 and tolerance $\geq 0,10$. Then all independent variables in this study are multicoliniarity free.

**Table 7. Autocorelation Test
Model Summary^b**

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.880 ^a	.775	.753	1.48765	1.680

a. Predictors: (Constant), Kompensasi Non Finansial (X3), Kompensasi Finansial (X2), Stres Kerja (X1)

b. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Kerja (Y)

The value of the DW is 1,680 where the value of $dU = 1,650$ so that the value $4 - 1,650 = 2,350$. This means that the DW value of 1,680 is between dU s.d $4 - dU$ which means there is no autocorrelation. Thus this regression model is free from the assumption of autocorrelation.

B. Hypothesis Test

**Table 8. T Test
Coefficients^a**

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.376	3.345		.411	.684
1 Stres Kerja (X1)	.318	.119	.336	2.679	.012
Kompensasi Finansial (X2)	.239	.070	.352	3.414	.002
Kompensasi Non Finansial (X3)	.433	.099	.482	4.362	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Kerja (Y)

Based on the regression equation above, it can be explained as follows:

1. The constant value (a) of 1,376 means that when work stress, financial compensation and non-financial compensation are assumed to be zero (0), then job satisfaction is worth 1,376,
2. The value of the regression coefficient of the variable work stress of 0.318 means that if the work stress is increased one by one, then the satisfaction of the work will experience an increase of the value by 0.318
3. The value of the regression coefficient of the financial compensation variable is 0.239, which means that if the compensation is increased one by one, then the job satisfaction will experience an increase of 0.239
4. The value of the non-financial compensation variable regression coefficient is 0.433 which means that if nonfinancy compensation is increased one by one, then employment satisfaction will be increased by 0.433.
5. Standard error (e) is a random variable and has a profitability distribution.

This obtained the following results:

1. Variable X1 work stress. known thitung (2,679) > ttable (2,039) and significant (0,012) < (0,05), then Ho rejected Ha accepted, meaning that on the work stress variable there is a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction in the Construction Company in Pekanbaru
2. Variable X2 financial compensation. Knowing thitung (3,414) > ttable (2,039) and significant (0,002) < (0,05) then Ho rejected Ha accepted, which means on the financial compensation variable there is a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction at the Construction Company in Pekanbaru.
3. Variable X3 non-financial compensation. Knowing thitung (4,362) > ttable (2,039) and significant (0,000) < (0,05) then Ho rejected Ha accepted, meaning on non-financial compensation variable there is a positive and significant influence on employee job satisfaction at the Construction Company in Pekanbaru.

**Table 9. F Test
ANOVA^a**

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	236.137	3	78.712	35.566	.000 ^b
	Residual	68.606	31	2.213		
	Total	304.743	34			

a. Dependent Variable: Kepuasan Kerja (Y)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Kompensasi Non Finansial (X3), Kompensasi Finansial (X2), Stres Kerja (X1)

That F counts as 35,566 with a significant 0,000 and the number of F statistical tables as 2,91. Thus, it is known that F count as $(35,566) > F \text{ table } (2,91)$ with a meaningful $0,000 < 0,05$. This means that simultaneously or simultaneously work stress, financial compensation and non-financial compensation have a significant impact on employee job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

- Work stress partially has a significant impact on employee satisfaction and based on the results of the linear regression test, the work stress variable is positive, which means that each increase in work stress of 1 unit will increase employee employment satisfaction at the construction company in Pekanbaru.
- The partial financial compensation has a significant impact on employee satisfaction and based on the result of the linear regression trial, the double variable of the economic compensation is a positive value which means that each increase in the 1 unit monetary compensation will increase employee employment satisfaction at the Construction Company in Pekanbaru.
- Non-financial compensation partially has a significant impact on employee job satisfaction and based on the result of the linear regression test of the double variable non-finance compensation value is positive which means showing every 1 unit improvement in leadership style then will increase employee employment satisfaction at the Construction Company in Pekanbaru
- At the same time or simultaneously, work stress, financial compensation and non-financial compensation have a significant impact on employee employment satisfaction at PP Construction Company in Pekanbaru with known calculations of $F (35,566) \geq F_{\text{table}} (2,91)$ with a significant $0,000 \leq 0,05$, and the determination coefficient (R Square) value of 0,775 equals 77,5% which means that the work stress variables, financial compensation and not financial compensations affect employee satisfaction of 77,5%

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